

Full Length Research Paper

Hematology and serum biochemistry of intact West African dwarf bucks fed varying levels of local brewers' dried grain with ber (*Ziziphus jujube*) leaves basal diets

Babale, D. M^{1*}, Iliya, Y.² and Dazala, I. U.¹

¹Department of Animal Production, Adamawa State University, Mubi, Nigeria.

²Madagali Local Government, Gulak, Adamawa State, Nigeria.

*Corresponding author E-mail: babaled@yahoo.com

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Effects of varying levels of local brewers' dried grain with ber (*Ziziphus jujube*) leaves basal diets on haematology and serum biochemistry parameters of Intact West African Dwarf goats were studied. Twelve intact animals were used in this study. Animals were kept in individual boxes for 8 weeks and fed the experimental diets consisting of ber leaves (*Ziziphus jujube*) as basal diet, supplemented with local brewers' dried grain at 50g, 100g, 150g and 200g designated as treatments T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄ respectively. Feed intake was measured daily and the body weight was measured weekly. At the end of the experimental period, blood samples were collected for haematology and serum biochemistry analysis. Parameters determined were proximate compositions of the experimental diets, haematology and serum biochemical indices. Haematological parameters determined were packed cell volume (PCV), Haemoglobin (Hb), Red blood cell counts (RBC) and White blood cell counts (WBC). Serum biochemical parameters were Blood protein, Albumen, Globulin, Glucose Blood urea nitrogen, Bilirubin, ALT and AST. Data obtained were subjected to Analysis of Variance

(ANOVA) in a Randomized Complete Block Design using SAS (2001) package. Where significant differences occurred among means, Duncan Multiple Range Test (Duncan, 1955) was used to separate them. Results showed that PCV, Hb, RBC, WBC, MCHC, MCH and MCV ranged from 34.50 - 42.50 %, 76.00 - 91.50 g/dl, 5.27 - 8.55 $10^3/\text{mm}^3$, 10.50 - 13.20 $10^6/\text{mm}^3$, 2.14 - 2.58 g/dl, 8.45- 14.42g and 3.95 - 6.74 fL, respectively. The blood indices (MCV, MCH and MCHC), were within the normal ranges indicating that the goats were not anaemic. Therefore the haematological and serum metabolites were within the established ranges for healthy goats suggesting that tannin concentration of *Ziziphus jujube* were well tolerated by the goats. It was thus concluded that the feeding of the *Ziziphus jujube* as basal diet supplemented with brewers' dried grain did not cause any major health disorders. The experimental diets are therefore recommended for fattening of goats.

Keywords: Haematology, Serum, West African Dwarf bucks, Ber leaves, Brewer's dried grain

INTRODUCTION

The West African Dwarf (WAD) goat is a trypanotolerant breed kept mainly for meat production and found within the savanna ecological zone of Nigeria.

The breed constitutes a major contributor to the animal protein intake of millions of people of the area (Okoli *et al.*, 2005).

Blood is an important index of physiological and pathological changes in an organism (Mitruka and Rawnshey, 2007). The primary function of the blood is to transport oxygen from respiratory organs to body cells (Duke, 2005) distributing nutrients and enzymes to cells and carrying away waste products (Jan *et al.*, 2015) thereby maintaining homeostasis of the internal environment (Bentricks, 2004). The various functions of the blood are carried out by the individual and collective actions of its constituents—the haematological and biochemical components (Akinmutimi, 2004). Haematological tests have been widely used for the diagnosis of various diseases and nutritional status of animal. The information gained from the blood parameters substantiate the physical examination and together with medical history provide excellent basis for medical judgment (Schalm *et al.*, 2005). In addition, it would help determine the extent of tissue and organ damage, the response of defense mechanism of the patient and aid in diagnosing the type of possible anemia (Schalm, 2005).

World Health Organization WHO, (2003) recommended the use of blood indices as an important medium to ascertain the health, nutritional and physiological statuses of animals fed different feeds. The nutritional and health status of animals especially pregnant ones cannot be compromised hence the health status of the animal requires close scrutiny and proper examination of the blood is important (Ibhaze, 2015). However, variations in blood parameters of animals are due to several factors such as altitude, feeding level, age, sex, breed, diurnal and seasonal variation, temperature and physiological status of animals (Mbassa and Poulsen, 2003). Previous studies have shown that changes in hematologic and biochemical indices are pointers to various disease conditions, even at sub-clinical levels and have been used to provide diagnostic and prognostic aids in some disease conditions (Jain, 2006; Taiwo and Anosa, 2008). Silanikove, *et al.* (1996) stated that activities of AST and ALT are indicators of damage to liver and muscle. That ALT is liver specific while AST is a general marker of tissue damage. Therefore ratio of serum AST to ALT can be used to differentiate liver damage from other organ damages (Nathwani *et al.*, 2005).

Forage shrubs and browses also tend to be productive in herbage yield and are able to provide good quality feed even in the dry season because of their deep rooted nature compared to grasses most of which are productive only in the wet season (Barnes, 2011). *Ziziphus jujube* is a small deciduous tree or shrub reaching a height of 5–12 meters (16–39 ft), usually with thorny branches. The leaves are shiny-green, ovate-acute, 2–7 centimeters (0.79–2.76 in) long and 1–3 centimeters (0.39–1.18 in) wide, with three conspicuous veins at the base, and a finely toothed margin. The deciduous *Ziziphus* species lose all of their leaves for part of the year depending on

variations in rainfall. In deciduous species in tropical, subtropical, and arid regions, leaf loss coincides with the dry season. They grow mostly in tropical forests but have also been found in stubbles, pastures, coastal ranges, tropical mountain areas, and wet to dry interior regions. The amount of fodder (including leaves and fruits) from Indian jujube available to livestock in Sahelian sandy pastures was only 0.5 kg/ha and 14.8 kg/ha in low lying pastures (Sanon *et al.*, 2005). Indian jujube leaves and fruits contain saponins. However, no problem related with these saponins in animal feeding was observed (Jain, 2006). The leaves and twigs of most *Ziziphus* species, including *Ziziphus mauritiana*, can be used as nutritious fodder for livestock. Leaves of Indian jujube are readily eaten by camels, sheep, goats and cattle (Azam-Ali *et al.*, 2006; Tewatia *et al.*, 2002). Indian jujube is among the preferred plant species by all classes of ruminants (cattle, sheep, goats, camels), and also donkeys, particularly during winter and early spring (Tewatia *et al.*, 2002). In the Sahelian rangeland of Cameroon, dietary preferences were higher for leaves of *Ziziphus* species, while pods and blossoms of other species were generally preferred (Ngwa *et al.*, 2000).

Special attention is paid to toxins or anti-nutritional factors such as tannins which can limit fodder utilization of plant resources (Ubani and Tewe, 2001; Rajendiran and Kardivel, 2002). Rhaman and Kawamura, (2011) reported that many forage plants fed by animals are high in oxalates. Oxalates are needed by plants for osmoregulation of some minerals but can be toxic to livestock (Rhaman *et al.*, 2013). These oxalates can be degraded to certain level by ruminants to harmless formic acid and carbon dioxide (Allison *et al.*, 2007). The high cost and to some extent unavailability of plant energy and protein sources especially maize and cotton cake respectively in livestock feed manufacturing and ration formulation on the farms has made interest to be focused on cheaper alternative sources such as brewers' dried grain (Ibhaze, 2015). Information on the effects of feeding varying levels of local brewers' dried grain with ber (*Ziziphus jujube*) leaves basal diets on hematology and serum biochemistry of intact West African dwarf bucks in the study area is scanty. The research was therefore carried out to bridge this gap.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study site

The experiment was conducted at the Livestock Teaching and Research Farm of the Faculty of Agriculture, Adamawa State University Mubi, and Nigeria. Mubi is located in the Northern part of Adamawa State. It lies on Latitude 9°11' north of the equator and Longitude 13°45' east of the Greenwich Meridian at an altitude of 696m above sea level. It is bounded in the South and East by

Republic of Cameroun. The State has a land area of 4,728.77m² and population of 245,460 (Saidu and Gadiga, 2004), it is situated in the Sudan Savanna zone of Nigeria. The vegetation type is best described as *Combretaceous* woodland savanna (Areola, 1983) which consists of grasses or weeds and shrubs collectively making 70% of the entire vegetation. Some of these grasses, weeds and shrubs are used as animal feeds. The area has two distinct seasons; Rainy season lasts for four (4) months and dry season that lasts for eight (8) months. Annual rainfall ranges from 700-900 mm with highest peak in August. The area has minimum temperature of 12.7°C in January and maximum of 37°C in April (Adebayo, 2004).

Sources of feeds

Feeds were obtained from two different sources in and around Mubi environs. The ber (*Ziziphus jujube*) leaves were obtained from the wild by lopping the trees and collecting the leaves and bagging after drying under the shade. Local Brewers' dried grain was bought from the local beer brewers.

Experimental animals and management

The experimental animals were bought from local markets in and around Mubi and Michika Local Government area, Adamawa State, Nigeria. Twelve (12) West African Dwarf bucks with average age of twelve (12) months weighing about 13±0.7 Kg were used for the experiments. The animals were castrated using burdizzo, then individually housed in wooden pens measuring 1.50 m² floor spaces and 1.50 m heights. The floor was made of concrete and covered with wood shavings to conserve heat and absorb animal urine. All the animals were dewormed, treated against ectoparasites; Beranil was used against hemoparasites and antibiotics were administered. At the end of the adaptation period of one week, they were tagged and randomly allocated to different experimental diets. They were weighed to obtain initial weights and balanced for the weights before embarking on data collection. There were four (4) treatments each replicated three times making twelve (12) experimental animals.

Experimental Diets

The experimental diets consisted of ber leaves (*Ziziphus jujube*) as basal diet, supplemented with local brewers' dried grain at 50 g, 100 g, 150 g and 200 g designated as treatments T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄ respectively as indicated in (Table 1). These diets were fed to the animals throughout the experimental period of 63 days. At the end of the experimental period, harness bags were used in collecting

faecal droppings to determine apparent digestibility of the test diets.

Parameters determined

Parameters determined were proximate compositions of the experimental diets, haematology and serum biochemical indices. Haematological parameters determined were packed cell volume (PCV), Haemoglobin (Hb), Red blood cell counts (RBC) and White blood cell counts (WBC). Serum biochemical parameters were Blood protein, Albumen, Globulin, Glucose Blood urea nitrogen, Bilirubin, ALT and AST. Ten (10) mls of blood samples were collected from two bucks in each treatment using sterile syringe and needle and then sent to haematology laboratory for haematological studies and chemical pathology laboratory for biochemical analysis in Adamawa State University Clinic Mubi. The blood samples were drawn from the jugular veins after restraining the animals. Three (3) mls of the blood was placed in a sterile sample bottle containing Ethylene Diamine Tetracetic acid (EDTA) for haematological studies and the remaining 7mls (without anticoagulant) was used for blood chemistry (serum metabolites) determination.

Haematological indices determination

The haematological parameters determined were packed cell volume (PCV), Red blood cell counts (RBC) and White blood cell counts (WBC) which were determined as described by Coles, (1986). Haemoglobin content was determined by cyanmethaemoglobin method (Coles, 1986).

Serum chemistry analysis

Blood urea concentration was determined by Nessler reaction (Tanis and Naylor, 1986). Serum total protein was estimated by the Biuret method as described by Nicole and Allen, (1985). Albumin was estimated by Bromo cresol green (BCG) method (Peter *et al.*, 1982) whereas globulin concentration was determined by difference between total protein and albumin. Blood glucose was determined by glucose oxidase method (Stone, 1954). Serum enzymes; Alanine transaminase (ALT) and Aspartate transaminase (AST) were determined according to the methods of Reitman and Olafadehan, (2011) and the metabolites (urea and Creatinine) were determined as described by Eun *et al.* (2009). Mean corpuscular volume (MCV) and mean corpuscular haemoglobin concentrations (MCHC) were calculated from packed cell volume, haemoglobin concentration and red blood cells values as described by Reitman and Olafadehan, (2011).

Table 1. Composition of experimental diets.

Feeds	TREATMENTS			
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄
BDG (g)	50	100	150	200
BL	<i>ad lib</i>	<i>ad lib</i>	<i>ad lib</i>	<i>ad lib</i>
Salt (NaCl) %	2	2	2	2

Table 2. Chemical composition of experimental feeds.

Parameters	Brewers' dried grain (BDG)	Ber leaves (<i>Ziziphus jujube</i>)
Dry matter (DM) %	9.00	85.79
Crude protein (CP) %	19.61	16.10
Crude fiber (CF) %	15.82	11.04
Ether extract (EE) %	6.50	4.40
Ash %	9.2	9.2

Data analysis

Data obtained were subjected to Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) using a Randomized Complete Block Design using SAS (2001). Where significant differences occurred among means, Duncan Multiple Range Test (Duncan, 1955) was used to separate them. Table 2 shows the proximate compositions of the experimental feeds. Both feed ingredients have high crude protein and moderate crude fiber levels being 19.61, 15.82 for brewers dried and 16.10 and 11.04 for ber leaves respectively. Though each of these feeds had adequate levels of nutrients, the brewers dried grain was used as source of by-pass protein and the other as source of degradable protein.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The blood biochemical profile and levels of serum enzymes of experimental goats are presented in (Table 4 and Table 5) respectively. Haematology of the goats indicated that the PCV, Hb, RBC, WBC, MCHC, MCH and MCV ranged from 34.50–42.50 %, 76.00 – 91.50 g/dl, $5.27-8.5510.77 \times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$, $10.50-13.20 \times 10^6/\text{mm}^3$, 2.14 – 2.58 g/dl, 8.45- 14.42g and 3.95 – 6.74 fL, respectively. The fact that the blood indices (MCV, MCH and MCHC), which are important for diagnosis of anaemia in most animals (Coles, 1986) were within the normal ranges indicating that the goats were not anaemic.

Haemoglobin

The mean haemoglobin levels across treatments ranged from 76.00 to 91.50 g/dl. These were significantly ($P<0.05$) different across treatments (Table 3). The mean level of total serum protein ranged from 5.80 to 6.20g/dl across treatments. There was no significant ($P>0.05$) difference among treatment means. The mean serum

albumin ranged from 3.40 to 4.67g/dl which differed ($P<0.05$) significantly across treatments. The mean globulin contents ranged from 2.27 to 2.50g/dl which also differed ($P<0.05$) significantly across treatments. The mean haemoglobin level of the experimental animals was within the normal range (8–12 g/dl) as per Kaneko *et al.* (1997) for goats. This suggests that the general health of all experimental goats in the present study remained optimum. Blood urea nitrogen (BUN) levels are an indicator of protein nutrition status of the animal (Baker *et al.*, 1995). The values of the BUN which ranged from 2.10 to .80mg/dl were higher than the normal range (10- 20 mg/dl) as reported by Kaneko *et al.* (1997) for goats. Blood urea nitrogen levels are similar to that reported by Jan *et al.* (2015) while working with similar experimental animals. Protein digestion in ruminants results in unused ruminal ammonia being transported to the liver via the portal blood where it is converted to urea. This together with urea from deamination of amino acids arising from post-ruminal digestion and systemic protein turnover then circulates in the blood (Hammond and Chase, 1996). Effects of the diets on serum enzymes and metabolites are presented in (Table 5).

Aspartate aminotransferase (AST) and alanine transaminase (ALT)

Mean AST level (IU/L) in serum of goats ranged from 7.67 to 7.97 IU/L with no significant ($P>0.05$ difference or interaction observed between the dietary groups. Mean ALT level ranged from 6.87 to 8.47 IU/L which differed significantly ($P<0.05$) among dietary groups. The activities of microorganisms in rumen increased the fermentation rates because of production of extracellular enzymes that lead to increased solubility of different nutrients specially proteins which increase in a form of ruminal ammonia as reported by Khattab *et al.* (2013). The comparable level of AST and ALT irrespective of dietary treatment, observed in this study reflects no

Table 3. Effects of diets on haematological indices of intact West African Dwarf bucks.

Parameters	TREATMENTS				SEM	Sig Lev
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄		
PCV	34.50 ^b	37.50 ^b	35.50 ^b	42.50 ^a	1.26	**
Hb	89.00 ^{ab}	91.50 ^a	76.00 ^b	91.00 ^{ab}	1.96	**
RBC	7.77 ^b	6.60 ^c	5.27 ^d	10.77 ^a	0.30	**
WBC	13.20 ^a	10.50 ^b	10.60 ^b	12.40 ^{ab}	0.40	**
MCV	4.44	5.68	6.74	3.95	0.05	**
MCH	11.45	13.86	14.42	8.45	0.06	**
MCHC	2.58	2.44	2.14	2.14	0.02	**

Total Serum Protein

Table 4. Effects of diets on serum proteins.

Parameters	TREATMENTS				SEM	Sig Lev
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄		
Tot. Prot	5.87	5.80	6.20	6.20	0.07	NS
Album	3.40 ^c	3.90 ^b	3.50 ^c	4.67 ^a	0.08	**
Globu	2.47 ^{ab}	2.27 ^b	2.30 ^b	2.50 ^a	0.06	**
Gluko	5.27 ^b	6.10 ^{ab}	5.27 ^b	6.17 ^a	0.05	**

Table 5. Effects of diets on serum enzymes and metabolites.

Parameters	TREATMENTS				SEM	Sig Lev
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄		
Bld Urea	3.80 ^a	2.90 ^b	2.10 ^c	2.77 ^{bc}	0.06	**
AST	7.87	7.67	7.70	7.97	0.16	NS
ALT	6.87 ^c	6.97 ^c	8.00 ^b	8.47 ^a	0.21	**
Biliru	8.90 ^{bc}	8.70 ^c	9.87 ^a	9.07 ^b	0.18	**

abc: Means with different superscripts within a row are significantly different (P<0.05), SEM: Standard Error of Means.

adverse effect of the diets on liver, kidney and muscle mass. This also suggests that the energy and protein intakes of experimental animals were sufficient to maintain body weight and to prevent muscle breakdown. Reduction in the values of PCV and Hb may indicate a low protein intake, liver damage or anaemia. Haemoglobin falls gradually in animals on a low protein intake, parasitological infestation or liver damage (Lindsay, 2007).

Conclusion

From the research findings, the absence of clinical signs of ill health as a result of tannin toxicity symptoms and the findings of the haematological and serum metabolites within the established ranges for healthy goats suggest that tannin concentration of *Ziziphus jujube* were well tolerated by the goats. It was thus concluded that the feeding of the *Ziziphus jujube* as basal diet supplemented with brewers' dried grain did not cause any major health disorders. The experimental diets are therefore recommended for fattening of goats.

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Authors' declaration

We declared that this study is an original research by our research team and we agree to publish it in the journal.

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